

IMPLEMENTATIONS OF RESPONSIVE CULTURE TOWARDS CAPABILITY MATURITY MODEL LEVEL AT PUBLIC HEALTH CENTERS IN JAKARTA, INDONESIA

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Abstract

This study was done by using observational, in-depth interview, triangulation and cross-sectional approaches using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test the hypotheses. These approach was used to investigate the impact of responsive culture on Capability Maturity Model at 37 Public Health Centers in Jakarta- Indonesia, with a total sample size of 269 respondents. The purpose of this research was to study the implementation of responsive culture and it's influenced to organizational citizenship behavior as well as it's implication to capability maturity model at Public health centers, in Jakarta, Indonesia. The findings showed that the responsive culture had directly and significantly influenced to organizational citizenship behavior. In addition, responsive culture also significantly influenced capability maturity model. So, it can be said that the more responsive of the organization mediated by the employees' citizenship behavior the higher the maturity level organization would be.

Keywords: Awarness Management, Organizational Commitment, Responsive Culture; Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Capability Maturity Model.

INTRODUCTION

Public health center is one type of health services provided by the government of Indonesia to improve health; prevent and cure disease within the community, and its vision is stated as 'Indonesia for a healthy community (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2018) [1]. In general, the public health centers must provide preventive, promoted, curative and rehabilitative services either through individual or public health efforts, either for in-patient or for out-patient care system. In order to provide comprehensive health care services to all communities, public health centers have several main medical care which include maternal and child health programs, birth control program, eradication of infectious diseases, nutrition improvement program, environmental health treatment, health education community, laboratory, health school, mental health care, and dental health care [2].

Public health centers must stand on continuous quality improvement to ensure service accountability. The strategy to improve service quality requires four sides: (1) the customer side, with all their needs and expectations, (2) the organizational side, which include performance improvement, (3) the medical care side, such as production service, costumers' service improvement process, and 4) the organizational culture side, to supports continuous improvement. All components of customers with all their needs, hopes and desires are at the heart of the strategy to improve the quality of services [2].

Performance improvements focus on improving various performance standards and increasing the consistency of conformance by all employees through process,

competence, caring and professionalism. Process of improvement is to increase work processes and systems which are cost-effective and directly forward the streamlined. Strategies to improve service quality will achieve optimal change if the level of organizational maturity can be identified to support the continuous improvement of service quality to achieve excellent service as a competitive edge of the business [3].

Capability Maturity Model is a model of maturity and process capability that can define the understanding of an organizational process in various fields. Capability Maturity Model consists of 5 levels of maturity: (1) Initial; (2) Repeatable; (3) Defined; (4) Managed; (5) Optimized [4]. The higher the level of Capability Maturity Model of a public health centers, the better it will satisfy the consumer demands [4].

With the burgeoning numbers of private medical facility, Public Health Centers should find a way to better itself and thrive in the competition. Therefore staff should have the skill to manage their work environment (job/role environment skill) when needed, even when their main task has yet to be over. In this regard, the staff can be said to be activity-oriented. Everything which takes place in an institution must be known and acknowledged by the local leader and, thus, in this regard, it can be said that this said leader should be people-oriented [5].

Responsive Culture is a culture in which an organization which applies it consists of members who display the characters mentioned above, namely sensitive, anticipative, and reactive, which materializes as (having) interest, replying, responding, answering, (having) appeals, (being) active, (having) initiative, and (being) proactive and are time-oriented, people-oriented, and activity oriented [6].

The leaders and managers of Public Health Centers are demanded to have new knowledge in accordance with the ongoing changes. This new knowledge does not only concern the quality of the results of health examinations that have high accuracy, but also concerns other needs of patients related to the health care process. Simply put, Public Health Centers are demanded to be more outward looking. To do so, the assessment of responsive culture will be related to the other concepts: awareness management of the leader, and commitment of organization members.

Organizational commitment is the extent to which a person is attached to the organization where he works. Nelson and Quick [7] argue that organizational commitment is the strength of an organization member to identify himself with the organization. This is where the difference lies with organizational loyalty. Loyalty to the organization is a small part of commitment to the organization, although in many organizations employee loyalty to their career is placed higher than loyalty to the organization [8]. Many employees use their dedication and loyalty to the organization simply as a tactic for career advancement.

Before an organizational leader commits, of course he must be able to self-awareness, then he must be able to recognize his environment (situational awareness), so that he can manage his awareness (awareness management). Situational awareness is the ability to identify, carry out an analysis process, and comprehensively translate critical elements of information about what is happening [9]. Awareness is knowing the situation that occurs around them and is an element of perception of the surrounding environment which concerns space and time [10]. This awareness is the basis for making the right decision to carry out an action in accordance with its goals or performance [9,10].

Objectives of Study

Addressing the major issues discussed above, the objectives of the study were:

1. To assess awareness management of leaders; organizational commitment, responsive culture, organizational citizenship behavior of leaders and administrative staff.
2. To analyze the effects of awareness management on organizational commitment, responsive culture, organizational citizenship behavior and capability maturity model.
3. To analyze the effect of organizational commitment on responsive culture, organizational citizenship behavior and capability maturity model.
4. To analyze the effects of responsive culture on organizational citizenship behavior and capability maturity model.
5. To analyze the effects of organizational citizenship behavior on capability maturity model.

Significance of Study

Currently there are more and more private health services, and Public Health Centers have to compete fiercely. This study was conducted to help the institutions improve their performances to serve better health services. Understanding how internal capabilities, which are indicated by organizational citizenship behavior of the members should be managed in order to adapt to the changing environment, can help the management maximize the attainment of goals and objectives.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Harrison [11], Schein [12], and Hofstede [13] organizational culture is a set of shared values and norms that controls the organizational members' interactions with each other and with other people outside the organization. Culture shapes and controls behavior within organization, and influences how people respond to a situation and how they interpret the environment surrounding the organization. The formation of organizational culture of a company or an organization could not be separated from the role of the head or leader and the leadership of those organizations. Schein stated that founder plays a very important role in creating organization's culture and becoming source of culture formation. In the following stage, it is the responsibility of leaders and managers to maintain and preserve the created culture.

In marketing, responsiveness could be understood as people who would be able to receive responses from outside, to react quickly and be ready to receive good suggestions from others – internally or externally. Carlos [14] said that responsiveness refers to the firm's ability to respond quickly to customer needs and wants. Responsiveness is also understood as how far the people control their emotion or friendliness or how they analyze situation properly when they make communication/contact with the other people. When responsiveness becomes a habit and is internalized within the people of an organization and embedded in organization's system, it becomes a culture of responsiveness. In accordance with this understanding, it can be defined that responsive culture as a culture of an organization within members of organization can be considered as sensitive feeling, anticipative

thinking, and fast reaction. However, if an organization expected to have a strong responsive culture, it is mandatory to have a strong employee's commitment and Awareness Management.

Commitment refers to the acceptance, involvement and dedication of the employees to the goals of organization [15]. Furthermore, it is also said that employees will try their best to strive for organization's objectives and will stay longer with the organization if that organization invests adequately to train and develop those employees. This argument is in line with the view of Hong Y. Park [16] that employees who have high commitment to their organization tend to have more involvement in positive behavior. These all finally can be concluded that employee commitment may influence the culture of an organization.

Jan Kraemer [17] stated two definition of Situational awareness. First, Situational awareness is the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and a projection of their status in the near future. Second, situational awareness is the ability to identify, process, and comprehensively translate the critical elements of information about what happened in the environment. Awareness is to know the situation around and an element of the perception of the surrounding environment involving space and time. This concept therefore can be used as a basis for the right decision making to take action that is in accordance with the objectives of an organization. In this manner, Endsley also add that situational awareness can be classified into the sequence of psychological awareness, which starts from the perception, attention, memory, and decision making.

The concept of situational awareness was developed during World War I and implemented in aviation industry in 1980s, when there was considerable pressure for pilots and air traffic controllers to develop better situational awareness. Despite having its roots in aviation, it has been suggested that the concept is equally applicable to human supervisory. This would mean that, a good leader of an organization must have better understanding of internal and external environment surrounding the organization, or namely Awareness Management [17].

To assess and measure Awareness management, three criteria can be used: perception, comprehension and projection. Based on these criteria, the top leader should have good perception or comprehension, and good ability to understand and interpret everything surrounding the organization. In the same manner, the leadership can also create the situation and condition as well as empower their employees to enhance employee's commitment for the benefit of an organization [18]. This in line with Feby Febrianti [19] argument that employee's commitment has a positive relationship with the leadership behavior. A nation's competitiveness depends on the ability organizational citizenship behavior. Sandeep K. Pandey [20] said Organizational Citizenship Behavior influence on satisfaction based the performance. Satisfaction based on the performance could not be separated from Awareness Management of the leader of an organization.

In fact, the Public Health Centers environment with the characteristics of high contact, customized, and personal services, need to improve competence of their services products in order to satisfy consumers, in addition, service quality is also determined by the process of serving to meet consumer demands. Associated with the process which is determined by the human resource factors, it can be said that there is a close relationship with the level of organizational maturity or Capability Maturity Model.

Conceptual Framework

As can be seen in the figure 1, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior as multi-dimensional. Some dimensions are modeled with responsive culture and organizational citizenship behavior as the dependent variables. It is suggested that organizational commitment has significant determinant of responsive culture and organizational citizenship behavior i.e. more commitment leading to higher levels of responsiveness and better organizational citizenship behavior.

Research Hypotheses

To examine these relations of management awareness, organizational commitment, responsive culture, organizational citizenship behavior and capability maturity model, research hypotheses was developed as following.

- H1: Awareness management, such as: perception, comprehension, projection, has positive effect on organizational commitment, such as: responsibility, loyalty, feeling guilty, care, humanity, unity.
- H2: Awareness management, such as: perception, comprehension, projection, has positive effect on responsive culture that related to time oriented, people oriented, activity oriented.
- H3: Awareness management, such as: perception, comprehension, projection, has positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior, such as: altruism, civic virtue, conscientiousness, courtesy, sportsmanship.
- H4: Awareness management, such as: perception, comprehension, projection, has positive effect on capability maturity model, such as: initial, repeatable, defined, managed, optimist.
- H5: Organizational commitment, such as: responsibility, loyalty, feeling guilty, care, humanity, unity, has positive effect on responsive culture that related to time oriented, people oriented, activity oriented.
- H6: Organizational commitment, such as: responsibility, loyalty, feeling guilty, care, humanity, unity, has positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior, such as: altruism, civic virtue, conscientiousness, courtesy, sportsmanship.
- H7: Organizational commitment, such as: responsibility, loyalty, feeling guilty, care, humanity, unity, has positive effect on capability maturity model, such as initial, repeatable, defined, managed, optimized)
- H8: Responsive culture, such as time oriented, people oriented and activity oriented, has positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior, such as: altruism, civic virtue, conscientiousness, courtesy, sportsmanship.
- H9: Responsive culture, such as time oriented, people oriented and activity oriented, has positive effect on capability maturity model, such as: initial, repeatable, defined, managed, optimist.
- H10: Organizational citizenship behavior, such as altruism, civic virtue, conscientiousness, courtesy, sportsmanship, has positive effect on capability maturity model, such as: initial, repeatable, defined, managed, optimist.

Based on ten hypothesis mentioned above, figure 2 was arranged to present the model of variable hypothesis construction or conceptual framework of research hypothesis.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research method of this study was cross sectional approaches using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The aim of this method was to develop a better understanding of the awareness management, organizational commitment and its relation to responsive culture and organizational citizenship behavior and implications on capability maturity model from the point of view of leaders and their staff at public health centers in Jakarta, Indonesia.

Sample

The study was based on the primary data collected from 37 public health centers that consist of leaders and staff in Jakarta, Indonesia with the total 269 respondents; classification of leaders and staff in public health centers tested was who had worked at least 3 years at public health centers.

Data Collection Technique

In collecting data, questionnaires were distributed to the respondents in thirty-seven (37) public health centers. Specific data collection of responsive culture and capability maturity model were done by in-depth interviews as pre-research and post-research. In addition, the researcher and team were doing observations. The assessment was done by using work place assessment at each public health center.

In this study, there are two types of questionnaires; First, questionnaires to assess awareness management were only filled in by only the leaders of the public health centers or their representatives. Second, questionnaires to assess organizational commitment, responsive culture, organizational citizenship behavior and capability maturity models were filled in by leaders and staff.

Furthermore, the interview was done the researcher and team, assisted by 2 Master of Psychology. The interview was conducted by referring the question on the questionnaires, while it was also recorded by digital device. The result of the interview was transcribed by transcriptional experts. Later, the result of the interview and the questionnaires were compared, if there was a discrepancy, the answers from the interview were preferred and considered as approaching the truth, because at the time of the interview the respondents had yet to know or read the questions on the questionnaires.

To get more accurate and reliable data, triangulation was used specifically to assess responsive culture and capability maturity models. The triangulation used as sources and methods to support quantitative data, by comparing and contrasting data from observations and documents collected.

Data Analysis

There were two steps of detailed statistical analysis were used to analyses data. First, descriptive statistics analysis was performed to extract the mean and standard deviation of underlying study variables core awareness management, organizational commitment, responsive culture and organizational citizenship behavior, capability maturity model and their dimensions. Second, the statistical package SEM, structural

equation modeling analysis was performed to understand the relationship among these variables was used for data analysis [21].

RESULTS

The responsive cultures conditions of the leaders and staffs of the Public Health Centers are depicted on table 1 and 2 (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Values of responsive culture before implementation

No.	Institution	Average			Responsive Culture
		Time-Oriented	People Oriented	Activity Oriented	
1.	37 (thirty-seven) Puskesmas Public Health Centers	13,83	9,88	9,83	33,54

Source: primary data, processed by researchers

Responsive culture values are divided into three categories as follows:

1. Unresponsive category : 0 - 36
2. Enough responsive categories: 36.01 - 72
3. Responsive category : 72.01 - 108

A value of responsive culture was at of 33.54. The results shown of responsive culture are presented in the following table 2 (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Values of responsive culture after implementation

No.	Institution	Average			Responsive Culture
		Time-Oriented	People Oriented	Activity Oriented	
1.	37 (thirty seven) Puskesmas Public Health Centers	18,56	19,60	17,45	55,61

Source: primary data, processed by researchers

When compared table 1 with table 2, it can be seen that there are an increase of values: time oriented, people oriented and activity oriented. This means that responsive culture can be accepted and implemented by both the leaderships and staffs of the Public Health Centers even though the increase is only in the responsive enough category, it has not responsive category yet

Significantly, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to test of hypotheses. Requirement for a minimum t-statistic value of 1.96 and the result showed as following.

- H1: Accepted. With awareness management set as the independent variable, and the various component of organizational commitment as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at 0.193 and t-statistic value of 3.486.
- H2: Not accepted. With awareness management set as the independent variable, and the various components of responsive culture as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at -0.050 and t-statistic value of 0.537

- H3: Not accepted. With awareness management set as the independent variable, and the various components of organizational citizenship behavior as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at 0.047 and t-statistic value of 0.491
- H4: Not accepted. With awareness management set as the independent variable, and the various components of capability maturity model as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at -0.036 and t-statistic value of 1.364
- H5: Accepted. With organizational commitment as the independent variable, and the various components of responsive culture as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at 0.290 and t-statistic value of 3.649
- H6: Not accepted. With organizational commitment set as the independent variable, and the various components of organizational citizenship behavior as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at 0.134 and t-statistic value of 1.354
- H7: Not accepted. With organizational commitment as the independent variable, and the various components of capability maturity model as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at 0.015 and t-statistic value of 0.477
- H8: Accepted. With responsive culture as the independent variable, and the various components of organizational citizenship behavior as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at 0.401 and t-statistic value of 5.758
- H9: Not accepted. With responsive culture as the independent variable, and the various components of capability maturity model as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at -0.015 and t-statistic value of 0.485
- H10: Accepted. With organizational citizenship behavior as the independent variable, and the various components of capability maturity model as the dependent variable, we found that the inner weight coefficient values obtained at 0.946 and t-statistic value of 47.156

The best model of the influence of awareness management and organizational commitment in association with responsive culture and organizational citizenship behavior which has implications for the capability maturity model can be illustrated in the figure 1 (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: The best model of the influence awareness management towards capability maturity model

DISCUSSIONS

Based on this model, it can be stated that organizational commitment and responsive culture had a very important role in the process of improving organizational citizenship behavior and capability maturity models because organizational commitment and responsive culture were moderating factors or a link between awareness management with capability maturity models. Therefore, in order to increase commitment to all aspects, it can be done by giving opportunities to employees to show their achievements, giving rewards and punishment, and giving opportunities to improve their education. In line with the theory of normative commitment by Meyer and Allen [15] which describes the responsibilities of an employee in an organization caused by socialization because it has been invested by the organization. Someone who has been invested by his company will be loyal and committed to his organization. If such conditions applied and were maintained for all employees, individual commitment to the organization can be increased, and ultimately the formation of responsive culture is quickly formed.

This finding is also in line theory which states that organizational culture had a strong influence on employee attitudes and behavior [22] which was similar to the results of Black's research which found that organizational culture tends to influence employee

works [23]. Therefore, it was important for the leaders of public health centers to always direct employees to have sensitive thinking and anticipatory behavior to produce good organizational behavior both internal and external.

Keep in mind that Responsive Culture is time oriented, people oriented, and activity oriented. Time oriented because some of the nature of responsiveness was answering, replying, and responding with time levels. People oriented because some of the nature of responsiveness such as: suggestions, efforts, appeals, or influences obtained from the subject of the leader. Activity oriented was translated into how to manage the work's environment for the benefit of others even though he was working. When the Responsive Culture has been formed, all employees will be ready to compete in this era of globalization.

Awareness management is a construct variable that refers to the perception, comprehension, and projection of one's awareness. In this case the leadership or those who represent, to the internal and external environment of the Public Health Centers (Endsley, 2000). The results of this study are in accordance with the results of Neville A Stanton et al in several groups of public vehicle drivers in the United Kingdom [24]. The finding showed an increase in their state awareness of their situation, meaning, the average value of perception to understanding then projection had been started. Jan Kraemer et al [17] also stated that understanding did not require the element of perception if data can be integrated and synthesized to produce an understanding of the relevance of the leadership's task. Meanwhile, in 2019, Emma et al proposed and argued that there was an increasing degree of awareness as information was processed at a higher level [25]. This proved that many Public Health Centers leaders already understood and had been aware of the situation and conditions that occur around them. Situational awareness did not have to contain three elements, namely perception, comprehension, and projection, but it could only perception [26] just like Endsley [25] which stated that the level of perception was the lowest level of situational awareness, however, to its correlation with the leadership's perception of the health laboratory. No data interpretation was carried out at this stage; all of it was intended to represent the initial receipt of the information in its raw form. The second level was understanding the situation at that time of the situation happened. Understanding can follow from the perceptual element (not requiring) if the data can be integrated and synthesized to produce an understanding of the relevance of the leadership's task.

It can be argued that understanding was important elements in order to get a picture of the events directly. In this way, Public health centers' leaders can make judgments about their actions and produce the desired results. It was in line with the opinion of Endsley [25] the level of understanding of the leadership showed the level of expertise at the Public Health centers.

The results of this study were consistent with Joseph 's study which found that employee satisfaction happened because management's expectations and needs were met, and It would affect their productivity [27]. The loyal aspect was an attribute that refers to the consistency of employees to behave that was more than the demands of the Public health centers. Loyal was identified as an attribute that was strongly influenced by the characteristics of debt related to the necessities of life. In this case, when the necessities of life can be met, the higher the employee's loyalty to the organization. Therefore, in order to increase commitment in all aspects, it can be done

by providing opportunities for employees to show their achievements, giving rewards and punishments, and providing opportunities to improve their education. Meyer and Allen's [15] theory of normative commitment which describes the responsibilities of a worker in an organization resulting from socialization because it has been invested in the organization. A person who has been invested by his company will be loyal and committed to his organization. If such conditions are maintained and enforced for all employees, individual commitment to the organization can be increased.

In the Responsiveness Space Conference, a person's response also concerns the level of time, how fast employees serve customers. All customer components with all their needs, hopes, and desires are the heart of the strategy because they are the ones who will drive improvement efforts. Performance improvement will focus on improving various performance standards and increasing the consistency of conformance by *Public Health Enterprises* staff through competence, caring and professionalism. Process improvement is a cost-effective and straight forward the streamlined improvement of work processes and systems [28,29]

The speed of service, both for internal and external customers, can accelerate the formation of organizational culture [30,31]. Services for internal customers can be in the form of meeting basic needs, for example providing opportunities and costs to increase education to a higher level for public health centers workers who have been working for at least two years. Services for external customers are services for Public Health customers. Respondents consider time oriented. Leaders have a role to play in the formation of a responsive culture. Leaders must always give rewards and punishments to staff in order to improve services to external customers of the Public Health Centers. In accordance with the opinion of [30,31] culture can be cultivated, maintained, and can even fade and die. Culture has an effect that greatly affects individuals and performance, even more than all the factors that are often discussed in the literature on organization and business [30,31].

The results showed that the most dominant time indicator was time oriented, it formed the responsive culture variable. This may be because the respondents have a lot of workload and must be completed as soon as possible. The indicator of time oriented as part of the responsiveness was answering, replying, and responding with time levels, it means that the speed of Public Health centers staff serving external customers and the speed at which Public Health centers leaders serve internal customers.

Organizational motives and personality self-evaluation were the core factors that can encourage the formation of organizational citizenship behavior, suggest that satisfaction with the quality of work life is the main determinant of the formation of organizational citizenship behavior of an employee[32,33]. In line with the results of Moh. Badrut Tamam's research [34], he stated that one of the factors that affect organizational citizenship behavior is culture and organizational climate. Moh. Badrut Tamam also said that organizational citizenship behavior is more influenced by personality or more precisely emotional intelligence than situational factors and working conditions, or OCB is a mediator or intermediary for these factors. Because based on work experience so far, it can be seen that many employees are satisfied with their working conditions and situations but still don't have extra behavior like this. It showed that the respondents work without considering standard operating procedures.

CONCLUSIONS

Responsive Culture is essential in increasing employees' attitude towards Organizational Citizenship Behavior, and thus increasing the Capability Maturity Model. The more responsive culture is being applied in the organization, the more organizational citizenship behavior will increase significantly. The formations of Responsive Culture were inseparable from the participation and commitment of the leadership. Responsive Culture can be implemented also other kind of institutions as long as they followed the procedures that has three dimension, such as time oriented, people oriented and activity oriented.

Authors' Contributions

Tjipto Rini is interested in environmental health research, especially, Public Health. In this research she had contributed in proposing idea, and correspondent. She has invented theory of Responsive Culture based on her research in many public health centers and education. However, she is currently working as lecturer at Master of Hospital Administration Department, in Esa Unggul University - Jakarta, Indonesia.

Tjipto Sajekti is interested in doing quantitative research, because she is an expert of statistics. She has been supporting this research by doing the statistical analysis. She is currently working as a lecturer at INABA University - Bandung, West Java, Indonesia.

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Competing Interests

The authors of this research declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate

The ethical approval of this research was taken from Ethics Committee of Health Polytechnic Institute II, Jakarta (Ethical Approval LB.02.03/KE/33/303a).

The consent to participate was given in written form to the 269 respondents before the questionnaires and in-depth interview was done.

Declaration

I hereby declare that all data and knowledge shared in this paper is correct and accurate. I solemnly declare that all the information furnished in this document is free of errors to the best of my knowledge. I hereby declare that all the information contained in this research paper is in accordance with facts or truths to my knowledge.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors of this research declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

Availability of Data and Material

The data are recording about in-depth interview that was done in Bahasa Indonesia. However, the data was saved in google-drive, the link of the data can be access as following.

https://drive.google.com/file/d/10A02DsY52BcwfmSQcWNVeQO4k_5iDhHX/view?usp=sharing

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iGTAGnsGBsAlxgw6JwtuPTrbmJ9-zst2/view?usp=sharing>

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1c4cpMih6bSwr2-8YmoFLM2CJOIZ_PHGT/view?usp=sharing

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